

```
1 FROM python:3.11-slim
2
3 WORKDIR /app
4
5 COPY requirements.txt .
6 RUN pip install --no-cache-dir -r requirements.txt
7
8 COPY president_v1_3.py .
9
10 EXPOSE 8000
11
12 CMD ["uvicorn", "president_v1_3:app", "--host", "0.0.0.0", "--port", "8000"]
```